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**Abomasal infusion of oleic acid and exogenous emulsifier alter fatty acid
digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows**

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Abomasal infusion of oleic acid and exogenous emulsifier alter fatty acid digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. *By dos Santos Neto et al., page XXX.* Fatty acids are key nutrients and optimizing their utilization is essential to improve the productivity of dairy cows. We evaluated the effects of abomasal infusion of 45 g/d oleic acid, 20 g/d of polysorbate-C18:1 (a nonionic surfactant), and both (45 g/d oleic acid + 20 g/d polysorbate-C18:1) on fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows. In conclusion, abomasally infusing either 45 g of oleic acid or 20 g of polysorbate-C18:1 improved digestibility of dairy cows. In contrast, providing both had no additional benefits and moderated the positive responses observed in the individual treatments with oleic acid or polysorbate-C18:1.

Supplemental Table S1. Milk fatty acid (FA) yield of cows infused with treatments (n = 8)

Selected individual FA, ³ g/d	Treatment ¹				SEM	P-value ²		
	CON	OA	T80	OA+T80		Oleic	Polysorbate	Oleic × Polysorbate
C4:0	50.3	52.9	52.2	49.6	2.18	0.99	0.60	0.07
C6:0	37.0 ^b	39.2 ^a	37.7 ^{ab}	35.5 ^b	1.86	0.97	0.07	0.02
C8:0	22.9 ^b	24.5 ^a	23.2 ^{ab}	22.1 ^b	1.43	0.48	0.03	0.01
C10:0	62.0 ^{ab}	65.6 ^a	62.0 ^{ab}	59.0 ^b	5.0	0.79	0.02	0.01
C12:0	74.9 ^{ab}	77.5 ^a	72.2 ^{bc}	69.6 ^c	6.67	0.99	0.01	0.09
C14:0	226 ^a	231 ^a	232 ^a	216 ^b	10.4	0.09	0.18	0.01
<i>cis</i> -9 C14:1	17.8 ^a	17.0 ^{ab}	18.1 ^a	16.1 ^b	1.17	0.01	0.50	0.18
C16:0	624 ^{ab}	631 ^{ab}	647 ^a	568 ^b	26.2	0.10	0.32	0.08
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	27.7 ^{ab}	27.9 ^{ab}	30.1 ^a	25.8 ^b	0.99	0.06	0.80	0.06
C18:0	122 ^b	138 ^a	138 ^a	124 ^{ab}	5.39	0.83	0.72	0.02
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	3.14	3.24	3.34	3.26	0.15	0.83	0.13	0.20
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	3.07 ^c	3.78 ^a	3.30 ^b	3.67 ^a	0.10	<0.01	0.20	<0.01
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	5.53	5.76	5.76	5.95	0.49	0.45	0.48	0.93
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	7.14	7.99	7.35	7.54	0.46	0.15	0.73	0.33
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	250 ^c	289 ^a	276 ^b	285 ^{ab}	7.20	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	7.86	8.02	8.43	8.42	0.54	0.75	0.06	0.72
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	29.4	32.0	29.3	30.8	0.55	<0.01	0.15	0.19
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	3.71	4.06	4.10	4.00	0.21	0.40	0.26	0.14
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	4.67 ^b	5.07 ^a	4.62 ^b	4.73 ^b	0.13	<0.01	0.01	0.05

^{a-c}Means in a row with different superscripts differ ($P \leq 0.05$); separation conducted only if Oleic × Polysorbate effect was $P \leq 0.10$.

¹Treatments consisted of no emulsifier infusion (CON, water only); 45 g/d oleic acid (OA, $\geq 90\%$ oleic acid); 20 g/d polysorbate-C18:1 [T80, polyethoxylated sorbitan esterified mostly with oleic acid ($\geq 80\%$)]; or infusion of both OA and T80 (OA+T80).

² P -values refer to the main effect of oleic acid, the main effect of polysorbate, and the interaction between them.

³Approximately 80 individual fatty acids were quantified. Only select fatty acids are reported in the table.

Supplemental Table S2. Milk fatty acid (FA) concentration of cows infused with treatments (n = 8)

Selected individual FA, ³ g/100 g FA	Treatment ¹				SEM	P-value ²		
	CON	OA	T80	OA+T80		Oleic	Polysorbate	Oleic × Polysorbate
C4:0	3.01	3.06	3.08	3.08	0.10	0.67	0.52	0.72
C6:0	2.21	2.26	2.20	2.20	0.04	0.49	0.26	0.43
C8:0	1.37	1.41	1.35	1.36	0.03	0.16	0.13	0.40
C10:0	3.69	3.77	3.61	3.63	0.16	0.25	0.03	0.51
C12:0	4.46	4.46	4.31	4.29	0.22	0.79	0.01	0.82
C14:0	13.5	13.4	13.6	13.4	0.15	0.07	0.35	0.80
<i>cis</i> -9 C14:1	1.06	1.02	1.08	1.01	0.08	0.02	0.89	0.51
C16:0	38.4	36.1	36.7	35.1	0.51	<0.01	<0.01	0.22
<i>cis</i> -9 C16:1	1.72	1.62	1.71	1.61	0.03	<0.01	0.84	0.96
C18:0	7.26	7.64	7.48	7.67	0.27	0.06	0.36	0.49
<i>trans</i> -6 to 8 C18:1	0.19	0.19	0.21	0.20	0.01	0.98	0.07	0.87
<i>trans</i> -9 C18:1	0.18	0.22	0.20	0.23	0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.31
<i>trans</i> -10 C18:1	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.37	0.04	0.46	0.37	0.51
<i>trans</i> -11 C18:1	0.43	0.47	0.41	0.47	0.03	0.08	0.91	0.71
<i>cis</i> -9 C18:1	14.9	16.8	16.1	17.8	0.35	<0.01	<0.01	0.73
<i>cis</i> -11 C18:1	0.47	0.47	0.51	0.53	0.03	0.45	<0.01	0.23
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12 C18:2	1.76	1.89	1.84	1.92	0.05	0.01	0.15	0.42
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>trans</i> -11 C18:2	0.22	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.01	0.22	0.83	0.69
<i>cis</i> -9, <i>cis</i> -12, <i>cis</i> -15 C18:3	0.28	0.29	0.28	0.29	0.01	0.10	0.71	0.73

¹Treatments consisted of no emulsifier infusion (CON, water only); 45 g/d oleic acid (OA, ≥90% oleic acid); 20 g/d polysorbate-C18:1 [T80, polyethoxylated sorbitan esterified mostly with oleic acid (≥80%)] or infusion of both OA and T80 (OA+T80).

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